

EVOLUTION OF CHILDREN'S LITERATURE IN INDIA

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ABSTRACT

Children's literature in India has undergone significant transformation over the past decade. Moving beyond traditional, didactic narratives, modern literature embraces diverse themes, perspectives, and intersectionality. Contemporary works depict real-life issues such as caste, gender, disability, and societal inequities, fostering empathy and inclusivity. Visual storytelling, too, has evolved, with illustrators playing a pivotal role in addressing mature themes. This paper explores these shifts, presenting a comprehensive review of notable works and their contributions to authentic and transformative storytelling for children.

Introduction. Contemporary writers have taken Children's literature in India by a much needed and never before storm. Moving over the idea of perceiving children as mini adults and works in progress in need of moral lessons even during pursuit of leisurely reading, new age children's authors radicalise children's literature by telling their stories from their perspective, in their words.

There has been an undeniable, deliberate shift from the didactic to the inclusive. Children's literature in India has evolved exponentially to bring to fore stories of real young people, narratives that explore real problems and deal with all that is happening around the Indian child in this day and age.

Discussion. Another significant change has been the acknowledgement of the diversity within the society in recent children's literature. In a revolutionary transgression, authors have moved on from telling the generic story of the one kind of "good" that the reader must conform to, and instead reimagines the protagonist. The heroes of these books are not obedient, silent, long held ideals of children but real young people who have questions, who refuse to conform, who are in the middle of major transitions in life, who are struggling with disabilities, children from unconventional families – the lens is one of representation.

In her essay *Representing Diverse Childhoods*, Tultul Biswas writes – "the Most prominent type of childhood that we find in children's books being published at present is that of a middle-class, often fair-complexioned, usually convent-educated, well-fed, fun-loving, privileged, heteronormative child. The two main characteristics of childhood that these books emphasise are 'Innocence' and 'Naivete' on the one hand and 'Naughtiness' and 'Mischievousness' on the other. "The characters in too many children's books have for long been created devoid of contexts or subjectivities. And when such characters are created, the image or perception of the reader the authors are writing for, is like that of a one-kind-fits-

all nature - an image is created off a reader who is mostly an urban middle class school-going, straight, male child. however we are seeing a gradual change in this scenario”, she observes.

For the longest time, children’s literature in India has overlooked complex issues such as caste, religion or gender and the diversity within the Indian sub continent has only been written about as if it were limited to being what Krishna Kumar notes as “attractive differences arising from geography and culture, while seeking to keep out of view the differences arising from inequality rooted in economic conditions and the caste hierarchy”.

The shift from the Didactic

Books that have addressed difficult issues tend to deal with them in isolation, thereby allowing no space for intersectionality, thus making these narratives unreal and hard to identify with. There is an increasing awareness amongst writers today and there are examples to the contrary. Kamla

Bhasin’s *Rainbow Girls, Rainbow Boys* addresses issues of gender stereotypes, disability, personal preferences and acceptance all at once.

Another refreshing example is Jacinta Kerketta’s fearless expression of the tribal experience through her first book for children *Jacinta ki Diary*. In one of her poems in the book, the narrator challenges the city people, steeped in privilege, to live the life they dare imagine for her own people. She writes -

कितने तो तुमने बाँध बनाये
कितने जंगल पहाड़ उजाड़े
पर बाँध का पानी – बिजली
हमारे घरों तक नहीं पहुँचता

हमें तुमने सौर ऊर्जा से चलने वाली
बत्ती थमा दी
तुम भी शहर में सौर ऊर्जा से बत्ती
क्यों नहीं जलाते ?
क्या तुम्हारी तरफ सूरज नहीं उगता?

Biksu, written by Varun Grover and published by Ektara, is another example of giving voice to the adivasi, the tribal experience. The book “explores a space in children’s books that is not often entered. It uses Madhubani art to create a graphic novel and the language used is chhotanagpuri. It is

the real life story of an adivasi boy big Biksu, and his growing up years in a residential school. Boarding school life is common enough and stories for middle readers, except that in this case it is a residential school deep in the jungles of Jharkhand, and is about the experiences of a newer caste boy from an interior village it is a world that young readers seldom encounter in the books they read the visuals tell the intimate story as much as the text.”, Radhika Menon writes.

While such reading might make the city reader uncomfortable, it works because it doesn’t serve the flawed notion that people are the same everywhere. Popular literature that presumes the middle class, urban child as its reader, prevents young learners from seeing the multiplicity of experiences and perspective. It causes them to otherise anyone different from themselves even later as adults. Writing such as that of Kerketta and Grover then sensitise the privileged to develop empathy , acceptance and inclusion. Asha Nehemiah’s *Behind the Lie* explores the often swept under the carpet theme of domestic violence from the perspective of Valli and Ramesh who live “under a cloud of fear because of their father, who has a frightening temper.” The book empowers not only by telling a story that doesn’t often find a voice in children’s literature, but also by guiding how a child can cope with violence at home and where they can seek refuge. The book ends with an abuse helpline number that is specifically meant for children seeking protection Vinayak Varma’s *Angry akku* warrants closer attention to the issue of acknowledging feelings of anger and resentment and regulating them. While traditionally, good children never do get angry, the protagonist of this composition is unabashedly

'Angry Akku' until she learns the emotional regulation with help from a parent and isn't angry anymore. Such representation of "unpopular emotions" in popular literature then tells children as well as adults that the focus needs to be on learning how to deal with them, instead of feeling guilty for being angry in the first place.

Published by Iktara, Ranu..Mai kya Janu? is Asghar Wajahat's first book for children and it fearlessly addresses almost every issue that has long been considered unfit for children's literature – caste, religion, gender stereotypes, social disparity and biases that comes from all of these. The book addresses intersectionality in surprisingly simple words- at once unassuming, unpretentious and

thought provoking.

The Power of the Visual

Evolution of the visual is another transformative aspect of modern storytelling. Illustration has come to play a role much more significant than merely supporting the written word. Some of the earliest picture books were published by the NBT and CBT in the 1950s but they were limited in number and confined to the socially acceptable, pleasant subjects. Also, these were primarily meant for the youngest of children, most times pre schoolers and often non readers. All of that has changed phenomenally in the last decade or lesser!

While picture books still adhere to the format of having no more than a thousand words and being no longer than 32 pages, those seem to be the only rules that remain unbroken! The new age picture books are transgressing like never before into the realm of the controversial, the uncomfortable and are telling stories to older children, young adults even. These books move from the utopia of hope and the convention of instruction to open a window into mature themes of difficult, sometimes confusing reality of growing up.

Richa Jha's *Mommies* is a delightful example of how far illustration has come in the modern storytelling meant for older children. The book challenges the "conventional views of motherhood that

reduce moms to a rule-bound gendered identity". It seeks to establish that all mothers are individuals and have their own personalities and preferences and the idea is more than reiterated through Priya Sebastian's bold realistic images of mothers, one page at a time, mommies that look, sound and behave differently.

Sagar Kolwankar's pathbreaking picture book *My Name is Gulab* comes to mind as a powerful story of a young girl who is called "Stinky Gulab" at school because her father works as a sanitation

worker, limited, even forbidden to do any other job, because of the caste he was born into. A deeply sensitive book that addresses one of the most shameful, dehumanising social evils such as this could not have been the subject of a children's picture book only a decade ago and yet, here we are, watching the long hush-hushed story unfold from a child's perspective.

Not a side hustle anymore when it comes to modern children’s literature, the journey and evolution of illustration sees seasoned artists such as Tejubehan create painstakingly intricate, fantastic worlds in books such as Salai Selvam’s *Mother Steals a Bicycle* and other stories.

Back in the eighties, one saw similar intricacy in Mickey Patel’s stunning illustrations in Sigrun Srivastava’s *Ghost Rider of Darbhanga and other stories*. Thankfully, the number of books that present conscious, responsible visuals are manifold now. Picture books have outdone themselves in addressing social issues while simultaneously challenging long held ideas about certain genres. A decade ago, biographies may not have made their way to the reading list of an eight year old.

Books such as Sandhya Rao’s *Dha Dhin Na* work hard to change that. In a first of its kind book by an Indian author and an Indian illustrator, *Dha Dhin Na* presents the biography of famous tabla player Zakir Hussain in a never seen before avatar. Brilliantly illustrated by Priya Kuriyan, the book breaks the barrier of intimidation that a young reader might feel towards biographies, conventionally reserved for older readers looking for a more serious reading experience.

Out of the shadows and onto the centre stage, illustrators are now telling stories that are entirely wordless! Traditionally, books for children recognise cognitive and linguistic abilities associated with

normal developmental sequences. "Books become inaccessible to children when their development does not follow the anticipated sequence across all developmental areas.", Namita Jacob and Teresa Antony observe. While the effort to create accessible reading materials for children with print disabilities are noteworthy, there is still a long way to go. Wordless books are a step in the direction of engaging with the plurality and the diversity.

If literature is going to inform and transform how young readers will think tomorrow, these delightful books go a step further in completely giving the autonomy and the responsibility of interpreting the pictures in an entirely subjective, individual capacity to their readers.

Drawing inspiration from lived experiences, from seemingly mundane everyday life, these books provide "strong visual sequential narrative, enabling the reader to follow from one visual to the next; creating the anticipation of flipping the page; good use of emotions, colours and semiotics.", Canato Jimo, the illustrator of *Snip*, an award winning wordless book, observes.

अम्मा by Kavita Singh Kale is a more recent and an excellent example of the wordless narrative for the emergent reader or the visually inclined. It is a story of a young boy looking for his mother in a fair. The anxiety and the fear at having been separated from a parent in a public place and the longing to be reunited with her is all depicted wordlessly, through pictures alone. In the absence of words, illustration assumes double the responsibility.

In one of the pictures in *अम्मा*, the child looking for his mother is depicted as the tallest, almost a giant like figure. Whether this is the size of the lost child's anxiety or a depiction of his wish to be present everywhere at once to find his mother is for the reader to decide. Since the setting is that of a village fair, each page is crowded with characters, all with a story of their own. This nearly wordless book then offers a lot to 'read'.

Created by teachers in a Shaheed Nagar school in delhi, the book *बस्ती में बाढ़* is a moving tale of how natural disasters affect different sections of the society differently, this highlighting privilege or the lack of it in difficult times. The story is about a young girl who watches her family and her neighbours struggle to protect themselves and their belongings in the face of a flood caused by excessive rain. The book observes that the neighbourhoods meant for the middle class or the affluent do not get flooded because efficient drainage systems in these parts of the city ensure safety. The story revolves around the anxiety the people in Shaheed Nagar feel over losing their belongings, the sadness that comes with their homes that the flood washes away but it ends with a community celebration when the water recedes. The book makes a poignant yet hard hitting observation that the working class immigrants who move from their home towns to seek work and a better life in the metropolitan city find that the city is not planned to suit their needs and has little to offer them.

Aai and I by Mamta Nainy is a heartwarming story of a little girl whose mother fights cancer and Nadya, by Debasmita Dasgupta is a moving portrayal of a family in the midst of divorce.

Conclusion

In the last one decade alone , children's literature in India has seen a marked shift from the overtly moralistic storytelling to a myriad narrative that attempts to see children as individuals who navigate their worlds with dilemma, confusion, dreams, fears and realities.

The fact that children's books today deal with issues which were taboo or at least reserved for adult conversation only a decade ago or even lesser, is a promise of authentic literature that comes from lived experience and represents diverse Childhoods. The fact that cancer, divorce, anger, domestic violence, disability, the dalit and the tribal experience, social injustice, disparity, equity and the lack of it, have made it to the pages of children's books paints a picture of hope like never before.

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